

Ontological Bayesian Fleet Management

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Abstract

Management and sustainment of large fleets is a key driver in cost reduction within the defense industry. The industry comprises many fleets which require a common solution for all similar systems to avoid siloed products. Additionally, many fleets involve diverse resources including people, machines, parts, etc. demanding a solution that maps data and domain knowledge in a flexible way. Northrop Grumman addresses this with a knowledge driven data architecture composed of reusable microservices and fleet management products, enabling the extraction and modeling of core structures consistent across all fleets while enhancing scalability. The solution ingests expert knowledge and complex data sources into its ontological data model and standardizes prognostic methods ranging from Bayesian inference to modern machine learning. In this paper we discuss the fundamental data elements and design principles required to model an abstract fleet. We also discuss how the solution maps data onto these abstract objects—hydrating an ontological domain. Finally, we address techniques used to enable the prognostic model abstraction needed to feed a data driven fleet sustainment solution.

Key Words: ontology, semantics, sustainment, reliability, supply-chain, digital-twin

1. Introduction: Fleet Management and Sustainment

Management and sustainment of large fleets and particularly of old large fleets is a problem which must be solved in many industries. It is perhaps most poignant in the defense industry, where faulty equipment could have serious implications on national and international security. As such, it is common in the defense industry to find many siloed fleet management and sustainment products often solving pain related to a small piece of a larger picture. These products largely perform the same sub functions of the larger need, but for different fleets. Each fleet requires certain data to feed into predictive models giving an outlook on sustainment activities such as supply chain, reliability, maintenance scheduling, etc. Rather than maintain many disparate products, it is reasonable to standardize and maintain a single, uniform, reproducible, and reusable solution. We propose that this solution is Ontology Driven Fleet Management.

1.1 Fleet Management, Conceptually

Definition 1.1 (Fleet). A collection of like assets which in concert accomplish a set of goals.

A fleet could be a set of delivery trucks that accomplish the goals of moving material throughout a given area or a set of fighter jets that aims to provide a capability within the larger battle space. This system of systems is a common concept and occurs almost naturally in many domains.

The fleet is an asset and must be maintained to continue to achieve its goals. This maintenance poses a significant logistical challenge and provides the opportunity of optimization, the goal of the fleet management system.

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Definition 1.2 (Fleet Management System). A system that tracks the necessary data and context to compute and optimize the probability of success of a given set of fleet goals while minimizing the allocation of resources.

A fleet may have many goals. When optimizing this space, it becomes necessary to prioritize these goals, a prioritization that may vary depending on the probability of success of each. This is where the concept of risk mitigation becomes helpful.

Definition 1.3 (Risk). The probability of an event occurrence and the associated impact of the event.

By computing and prioritizing the risks to the fleet, and minimizing the associated cost to mitigate, as shown in Figure 1, the total cost of system maintenance can be optimized.

Figure 1: A Fleet Management System should minimize the cost needed to maintain the target system risk level. However, not all mitigations are feasible resulting in a need to determine attainable risk mitigations.

The cost associated with fleet sustainment can be broken into two major categories 1. personnel i.e., human labor hours and 2. capital. As both are finite, it is insufficient for a fleet management system to only determine cost. The attainability of the mitigation Figure 1 must be computed as well. This is the true goal of a fleet management system, to serve the end user or organization a set of attainable mitigations allowing action to be taken to maintain the system in an optimized fashion.

To determine risk and allocate resources for fleet sustainment requires the integration of a massive amount of data and context, many of which are discussed in [1]. The underlying architecture required for these integrations and computations can be reusable and an ontology driven solution enables the needed generalization and reusability.

2. Ontology Driven Data Solutions and Reusable Architectures

In data processing, context is key. A typical approach is to embed this context into a codebase and levy that codebase on a given data set to derive some insight. This approach first builds the knowledge into the ridged structure of the codebase which works well for a single solution but becomes over-specified to that use-case to be generalizable. When the system changes or similar knowledge is needed by another system the codebase often needs to be refactored. This refactoring can be costly particularly if the codebase is not

declaratively DRY (Don't Repeat Yourself) and encodes the same or similar knowledge repeatedly in multiple locations.

Another solution is to capture the context in an ontological knowledge model or meta-model and utilize code to pipe and tag data as described by the ontology. In this approach, if the ontology is generalized, the code base becomes extremely reusable, and when the system itself changes the knowledge/meta model is refactored and the codebase remains largely intact. "The migration of solutions to new problems depends heavily on the ability to use metamodels and in particular on using a common layered metamodel to organize and map existing standards." [2] This approach can also be utilized to create knowledge graphs with little additional effort. Allowing for reasoning beyond what is developed in the initial codebase. This is the benefit of Ontology Driven Data.

2.1 Ontology Driven Data

We start with a few definitions.

Definition 2.1 (Ontology). A formal structure of knowledge representation that can be used for reasoning and captures a set of concepts and categories in a subject domain and shows their properties and the relationships between them.

Definition 2.2 (Ontology Driven Data). Data that is structured, tagged, and stored in accordance with a governing ontology.

Definition 2.3 (Knowledge Graph). A graph database that is structured in accordance with a governing ontology and maintains relationships as first class data artifacts.

The goal of ontology driven data is to bind the knowledge associated with leveraging the data to the data itself. Functionally, and in the case of fleet management, this means mapping physical and abstract constructs of the fleet of systems in an ontology that is then utilized in congruence with the system data to generate the associated knowledge graph. By doing so, data structures can be read natively without having to read associated documentation or crawl through a codebase. This allows for the knowledge to become programmatically consumable.

This binding of data and ontology is accomplished by systematically mapping each element in the governing ontology to a programmatic process. This process is a piece of declarative code and creates and categorizes the individual data elements. Often these data elements are stored in a graph database and results in a knowledge graph. This approach may feel overly complex if a domain space is sufficiently captured by a given database schema. However, it is in the integration across multiple databases and digital tools where the overlapping schemas do not neatly align, that the power of the ontology driven data approach becomes visible.

It is often useful to break the ontology out by domain to reduce the cognitive load during either ontology development or reading. These domains are interrelated forming the master ontology as shown in Figure 2. These domains can be developed by the domain subject matter experts, minimizing the amount of cross training required to develop the end solution.

Figure 2: Master ontology composed of multiple domains distinguished by colors.

Now let us demonstrate an example of ontologically abstracting a problem space.

2.1.1 *Ontology Abstraction Example*

Let us consider the example of a fleet of delivery vehicles. These vehicles are largely the same in makeup and design and undergo some system maintenance to maintain the assets. This maintenance may need to be performed by multiple types of technicians depending on the system. The systems have some hierarchy of assemblies which may be filled by many different parts, all filling the same need, that are manufactured by multiple suppliers. Figure 3 demonstrates a subset of this type of use-case.

Figure 3: Delivery truck use case ontology

Obviously, this model is fairly tailored to a truck, and would become extremely large in a representation of the entire system. Instead we abstract the underlying structure and represent that in our ontology, as shown in Figure 4. The System has components that are arranged in a hierarchy that are fulfilled by parts which are manufactured by a supplier.

The Maintainers service given components. This ontology is then mated to the data which is streamed into a knowledge graph with the associated ontological elements giving us the exhaustive model with much less effort. This ontology is rather generalized allowing for the applications across many systems. It is not difficult to conceptualize how the data for a fighter jet could map into this structure.

Figure 4: Generalized ontology allows for the dynamic data driven generation of a knowledge graph.

Now let us consider the fleet again. This ontology seems to represent a given system well but when modeling the system of systems, it falls short. This is where it is helpful to separate the conceptual and physical models in the ontology. Figure 5 demonstrates this separation. The "Assembly Type" makes up the collection of needed assemblies for a given system to be built, but it is the actual installation of part instances into a physical location we call the "Assembly Instance Socket" that forms each physical asset.

It is this assembly instance socket ontological element around which almost all data needed to generate predictive system-specific models pivots.

Figure 5: Useful ontological distinction between physical and conceptual components and hierarchies that make up systems.

2.2 Logical, Physical, and Potential States an Ontological Model

Again, the goal is organizing data in a way that enables future state prognostics and identification of feasible risk reduction actions for a system. The ontological modeling is simply a means to this end. When developing the ontology it is helpful to extend the type and instance separation shown in Figure 5 to the entire data organization paradigm. Figure 6 shows the three data organizational layers that are used. The Logical layer is largely the

knowledge or conceptual model. It is an understanding of this layer that often makes a subject matter expert. The Physical layer is the collection of physical observations that are organized by the logical layer. The Potential layer is the inferences built on the Physical layer.

Figure 6: Convenient separation of modeling categories during ontological design.

Expanding these layers in the configuration, assembly, and part concepts as shown in Figure 7 we find the three mirror across the three layers intuitively. By organizing the data in this manner, a digital twin (Definition:2.4) is created.

Definition 2.4 (Digital Twin). A set of virtual information constructs that mimics the structure, context and behavior of an individual / unique physical asset, or a group of physical assets, is dynamically updated with data from its physical twin throughout its life cycle and informs decisions that realize value. [3]

Figure 7: Logical, Physical, and Potential models expanded around the Type, Instance paradigm.

Much of the data for a fleet management system is collected during the use and sustainment of the system. This data is most often tied to either the Assembly Socket Instance or the Part Instance ontological elements. Examples of data tied to the Assembly Socket Instance are odometer readings for a vehicle or flight hours for an aircraft. Data tied to a Part Instance is often collected during repair and testing when a part's failure modes are diagnosed, and the part is refurbished. In the case of sensor readings for instrumented parts, these data are often tied to both the Assembly Socket Instance and the Part Instance that was installed at the time of collection. The data contained in the Physical Model is collected to generate the Potential Model.

3. Common Transformations and Ontological Threads

In the domain of fleet management, there are several common data transformations or ontological patterns. These can be features that are used in a predictive model to generate some potential state inference and associated distribution. The baseline model frequently used for component reliability is shown in 1.

$$X_i|\gamma, \beta \sim \text{Weibull}(\gamma, \beta) \quad (1)$$

Where X_i is the time to failure, or cycles to failure, and γ and β are the shape and scape of the Weibull distribution respectively. Ideally, the γ and β have informed priors based on manufacturers specifications which are tied to the part type.

To fit these models we need to compute the input features for all currently fielded and past fielded components. For time to failure, the time a component has spent installed at a given assembly socket instance, referred to as the "time in place" must be computed. For the cycles to failure, the number of cycles a given piece of equipment has undergone, such as power or mechanical cycles, referred to as the "cycles experienced" must be computed.

3.1 Time in Place and Time in Use

To generate a reliability model for a given part type, we track the time each part instance of the given part type spent installed at an assembly socket instance, and if the removal was due to a scheduled maintenance event pre-failure or due to an unscheduled maintenance event post-failure. The ontology depicted in Figure 8 is used to compute this.

Figure 8: A standard ontology and transformation showing the time a component has spent installed at a given assembly socket instance, and whether the removal was due to scheduled or unscheduled maintenance.

Often the time in place is a less appropriate feature than the time in use. Consider the fleet of fighter jets or delivery vehicles, for many parts, the time a piece of equipment sits in the assembly is less indicative of failure than the time spent in flight or driving. To compute the time in use, we augment the ontology slightly as shown in Figure 9 by expanding the time in place from a time count to a time window. This window identifies which flights/routes have been performed, which are then aggregated to compute the time in use.

Figure 9: Cross referencing the time in place window with the flight/route time node allows for the flight-time in place or drive-time in place to be computed.

3.2 Cycles

Another feature that is a good indication of reliability is the number of cycles a piece of equipment undergoes prior to failure. For example, the number of times an engine is started prior to the starter failing, or the number of landings for the landing gear. To compute this metric, largely the same ontology is used as for the time in use. The time in place window contains cycles experienced by the assembly socket instance, which are aggregated as shown in Figure 10.

Figure 10: Cross referencing the time in place window with the cycles an assembly undergoes allows for the number of cycles experienced by the part instance in to be computed.

With these ontological elements modeled within the fleet management system, all of the underlying transformations and relationships between nodes remain consistent across applications (e.g., the ontology is the same whether we are looking at an aircraft or delivery truck fleet). It is only the mapping of maintenance data and assembly information that changes. This generalized architecture allows for rapid deployment of the fleet management platform, and minimizes the sustainment efforts associated with the architecture itself.

4. Modeling Methods

Computing the reliability of the system and its components is critical to identifying both the system’s ability to perform its mission and determining what actions should be taken to maintain the system and reduce risk.

In addition to the reliability of the system, anticipating the volume of failures for each part type is key to determining supply chain needs. Using reliability and failure, we can compute risk and cost and suggest sustainment actions. This requires a combination of an array of modeling techniques largely rooted in Bayesian inference with the ability to inject alternate modeling capabilities as needed.

The Ontology Driven Data layer enables the linkage of models to their associated assembly type and assembly socket instance. This linkage allows for transparency, by lending the ability to trace a digital thread (or ontological pathway) from an inference back to the data that was used to train the model.

4.1 Baseline Models

It is not uncommon for the number of assembly types required by a configuration type to extend into the tens of thousands. This massive load of models requires a baseline approach, which can be tailored as necessary.

Commonly, for the baseline, two models are useful:

1. The component reliability across the fleet
2. The failure rate across the fleet

4.1.1 Component reliability

For the component reliability, a baseline model is constructed based on the time in use to failure computed as shown in 9. These baseline models are composed of a Weibull distribution likelihood and an uninformed prior as shown in Eq. 2 unless a prior is available, based on the part type manufacturer specifications. These manufacturers specifications are ontologically related to the part type as shown in Figure 11.

$$\begin{aligned}
 X_i | \gamma, \beta &\stackrel{iid}{\sim} \text{Weibull}(\gamma, \beta) \\
 \gamma &\sim \text{Exponential}(\theta = 1), \\
 \beta &\sim \text{Normal}(\mu = 10, \sigma = 10)
 \end{aligned}
 \tag{2}$$

Figure 11: The manufacturer’s part specifications are used to create an informed prior. If these nodes are not present, then an uninformed prior is used.

Parameter distributions for γ and β in Eq. 2 are generated by fitting the observed time to failure for each part type using Markov Chain Monte Carlo sampling. Time in use durations for part instances that are removed prior to failure due to scheduled maintenance are left censored. A thorough explanation on the methods used to fit these models is discussed in [4].

After parameter distributions have been generated, we can compute component reliability via Eq. 3.

$$R(t) = 1 - F(t) \tag{3}$$

Where $F(t)$ is the cumulative distribution function of the model.

Each fielded component has a unique reliability distribution based on its observed time in use. We are able to compute these reliability distributions at any future time for each Assembly Instance through the conditional reliability Eq. 4 [5].

$$R(t|T) = \frac{R(T + t)}{R(T)} \tag{4}$$

Where T is the observed use-time and t the time from T at which the reliability metric is desired. These reliabilities are critical to computing system performance and risk and for optimizing the fleet sustainment effort.

This baseline model of the use-time to failure is sufficient for the majority of components. To determine the components that require further tailored models, an accuracy metric is computed for each. The accuracy is a Bayesian p-value comparison between the observed failures and a posterior predictive distribution. More details are given in [4]. Utilizing the computed accuracy metrics, systems that require a further tailored model can be identified.

Note that for equipment where cycles to failure are an available feature, the same baseline model can be used by exchanging X_i in Eq. 2 to represent cycles to failure rather than time to failure and adjusting the priors.

4.1.2 Fleet Holistic Failure Rates

Another baseline model that is useful is a failure rate model for a given part type for the entire fleet. This is a simple model that enables the identification of anticipated load on both the supply chain and the maintenance teams sustaining the fleet.

The baseline model utilizes the negative binomial distribution, Eq. 5.

$$\begin{aligned}
 F_i | r, p &\stackrel{iid}{\sim} \text{NegativeBinomial}(p, r) \\
 p &\sim \text{Beta}(\alpha = 1, \beta = 1) \\
 r &\sim \text{Exp}(\theta = 1)
 \end{aligned} \tag{5}$$

Where F_i is the observed failure rate and p and r are probability and the number of trials in the negative binomial distribution respectively. The dual parameterization of the negative binomial distribution affords the model sufficient flexibility to model a large variety of components.

Parameter distributions are sampled through a Markov Chain Monte Carlo process for each assembly type, yielding a unique parameterized model for each assembly type. Using this model, anticipated failure distributions can be computed. Often, failure rate distributions are projected one to two years forward to determine if sufficient spares are available or need to be procured.

Accuracy of these models are computed using a Bayesian p-value that compares the observed failures to the predicted failure distribution. This enables the identification of assembly types that need a tailored model.

4.2 Prognostics Methods and Tailored Models

After the baseline models have been computed, the question becomes how to model systems for which the baseline model performs poorly. Depending on the system data available there are several options available for generating a prognostic model and determining reliability. Figure 12 depicts these modeling techniques and some associated metrics.

Figure 12: Technical approaches to prognostics [6]

The baseline models belong at the bottom level of the pyramid. Many systems can be sufficiently supported at this level through a tailored model. While significant effort has gone into standardizing both shallow learning and deep learning methods in libraries such as Scikitlearn and Keras, lowering the barrier of entry to the middle layer of the pyramid, data sets that are sufficiently large and unbiased to utilize these techniques are not common for highly reliable fleets of systems as found in the defense industry. As a result, the middle layer tends to have less applicability on these systems. The top layer of the pyramid offers highly specific and powerful modeling capabilities that rely on physics models to provide context that would otherwise come through a large dataset. These models can provide reliability and remaining useful life metrics early in the life cycle. Due to the cost associated with developing these types of models, they are typically reserved for mission critical systems. There are a variety of libraries that enable the top pyramid layer, though many target a research audience and as a result, can be difficult to utilize in a production setting. [7]

Selecting a modeling approach to develop a tailored system model depends largely on the available data. Metrics such as the criticality of the component to the mission, the number of fielded assemblies in the fleet, and component cost play a large role in model selection. A Fleet management system that is modeled ontologically allows for extremely granular modeling and analytics that span the three layers of the pyramid as needed.

4.3 System Reliability

Thus far, we have discussed the modeling of each individual component and using those models to determine assembly instance reliability distributions. These are the bottom two layers in Figure 7. To determine the system reliability, each assembly instance reliability distribution can be combined using a fault tree, Definition 4.1.

Definition 4.1 (Fault Tree). A logic diagram that displays the relationships between a critical event, typically a system failure, and the causes of the event, typically component failures. [5]

The Ontology Driven Design methodology makes extracting a fault tree simple using the Assembly Instance Socket and its Has Child relationship (see Figure 7). If there is no redundancy in the systems, and each system is critical to the mission then the Has Child

relationships between assembly instance sockets would be sufficient to roll reliability distributions up to parent assemblies; essentially treating each relationship as running through an "or" gate. For systems with more complex fault trees, a gate node needs to be added to the ontology as shown in Figure 13a. Figure 13b depicts an example knowledge graph that shows how the fault tree would be rendered for a system that had two redundant subsystems each of which have only critical child components.

Figure 13: Fault Trees can be represented ontologically by adding a node and two edges to the assembly socket reliability distribution nodes.

With the addition of the fault tree mechanics, the fleet management system can determine each individual reliability and use these to calculate the collective risk to the fleet mission. Using the same Has Child hierarchy structure and the fault tree, a fleet management system can identify which systems contribute most to the mission risk and suggest actions to mitigate this risk.

4.4 MLOps

After any model is developed, it can be deployed and monitored to generate trustworthy predictions in a production environment. The automation of this process is MLOps (Machine Learning Operations).[8] In an ontological fleet management architecture, the model lifecycle post-research is captured ontologically and mapped to the associated features on which it was trained and to the system integration point to which it pertains, as shown in Figure 14.

Figure 14: Example of MLOps ontology

In the case of the Bayesian baseline models discussed in section 4.1, the part type reliability model may map to many part types, however the feature data path would only map one trained model instance to a single part type. Once deployed, the model is monitored for drift. This drift is measured as a Bayesian p-value of observed failures as compared to the posterior predictive distribution of failures over time. Baseline metrics and process controls are set on the model drift to initiate retraining events. Often, in addition to the model drift triggering a retraining event, models are retrained on a periodic cycle.

In the case of tailored models discussed in section 4.2, the model would mostly be tied to an individual part type and at most a small set of part types.

One benefit of the ontology approach is the ability to trace each trained model to the feature data that was used to create it. Each prediction can be mapped to the model, then to the data used to generate and train the model. This model transparency is key in a user's trust of the fleet management system.

4.5 Cascading Analysis

Thus far we have focused largely on the system and assembly reliability. However, fleet management extends beyond understanding the reliability and associated risk of system failure. Quantifying sustainability 4.2 and supportability 4.3 are key to maintaining the fleet and ensuring its goals are met.

Definition 4.2 (Sustainability). A measure of the capability to either produce or sustain parts for the desired period of time.

Definition 4.3 (Supportability). The ability to support a system without depleting or overextending limiting resources such as people-power in the form of mechanic time.

For example, taking a fleet of fighter jets, the fleet may be sustainable because the parts to repair them are not obsolete and can be procured, but the system may not be supportable because the skill set to install and replace the components is limited and the failure rate is outpacing the maintenance schedule.

Alternatively, in the delivery vehicle example, perhaps the fleet is supportable, but the fuel tank has a known fault to the manufacturer and as a result it will no longer be produced, rendering the fleet unsustainable.

In either case, factors beyond the system itself are limiting, resulting in an inability to meet the long-term goals of the fleet. Action must be taken to mitigate the risks to sustainability and supportability. Here, we introduce the concept of Cascading Analysis in which a series of stacked dependent predictions result in a possibility space in which a solution can be optimized. Figure 15 depicts an example of elements that must be combined to enable the identification of an optimized solution as it pertains to fleet management.

Figure 15: Cascading Analysis as pertaining to a series of fleet management domains and the identification of an optimized solution to maintain the system.

The Cascading analysis is largely computed through Monte Carlo simulation, propagating uncertainties through each layer. The benefit of baseline models and many tailored models being rooted in a Bayesian framework, allows for posterior distributions to be cascaded through the network naturally propagating uncertainties.

5. Conclusion

In this paper, we explored the benefits of building a fleet management system on an ontological framework to enable generalization across different types of fleets. We explored the benefits of two generalized baseline Bayesian models to enable system reliability computation and risk identification and mitigation. We have found that the bulk of the difficulty in fleet management is a result of data management and domain context and that addressing this through ontological data integration enables significant insights using simple modeling techniques. Propagating these insights through a series of layered analysis across different domains allows for the bounding of a possibility space, enabling the optimization of the fleet, though minimization of cost and risk.

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